

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D3.3 Anonymisation and Synthetic Data Algorithm

(Version 3.0, 24/07/2023)

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Deliverable:	D3.3 Anonymisation and Synthetic Data Algorithm	
Work Package:	WP3	
Due Date:	31 Jul. 2023	
Submission Date:	24 Jul. 2023	
Lead Beneficiary:	VICOM	
Version:	3.0	
Status:	Submitted	
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Keywords:	Anonymisation, Synthetic Data Generation, Shareable Data	
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	06/06/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	First version of TOC, Abstract and Executive Summary
1.1	12/06/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	First version of Introduction and Figures of Section 3.
1.2	19/06/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	Finished first draft of Section 3.
1.3	20/06/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	Finished first draft of Section 2
2.1	21/06/2023	Imanol Isasa (VICOM)	Started first draft of Section 4
2.2	21/06/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	Finished first draft of Section 5
2.3	22/06/2023	Imanol Isasa (VICOM)	Finished first draft of Section 4
2.4	26/06/2023	Francisco Londoño (VICOM), Gorka Epelde (VICOM), Imanol Isasa (VICOM), Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	Internally reviewed the entire document. Ready for review by the reviewers.
2.5	20/07/2023	Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	Incorporated changes suggested by reviewers.
3.0	20/07/2023	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)	Ready for submission

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
SDV	Synthetic Data Vault
NDM	Non Data Model
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ER	External Researchers
SDG	Synthetic Data Generation
SD	Synthetic Data
CSV	Comma Separated Values
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
STSG	Synthetic Time Series Generation
DGAN	DöppelGANger
WGAN-GP	Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network with Gradient Penalty
TS	Time Series

Abstract

This deliverable, associated with Task 3.4 (Anonymisation mechanism and Synthetic data engine toolkit development) of WP3 of the VITALISE project, reports on: 1) the anonymisation and synthetic data tools used for the shareable data publishing and, 2) access workflows incorporated in the VITALISE service architecture (presented previously in D3.1). The first part of the document gathers and explains some basic concepts about anonymisation and synthetic data generation. Next, it describes the implemented workflows for the shareable data publishing and access service. Following, the document presents the developed experimental and scientific work related to synthetic data generation for the VITALISE project, together with the obtained results. Finally, conclusions on the current development status and experimental work are reported.

Executive summary

This deliverable is of report nature as specified in the GA. The deliverable aims to present the anonymisation and synthetic data techniques used for the shareable data publishing and access workflows incorporated in the VITALISE information and communication technologies (ICT) tools that are being developed in WP3.

The main aim of using anonymisation and synthetic data generation techniques in the VITALISE ICT tools is to make sensible and private data generated from Living Labs (LL) accessible for external researchers. Using the VITALISE Discovery Portal, external researchers can download anonymised, synthetic or limited data versions of the real data hosted in LLs for developing, testing and debugging their processing scripts on highly realistic and representative data with no risk for re-identification of individual subjects.

The reported information in this deliverable mainly resulted from Task 3.4 (Anonymisation mechanism and Synthetic data engine toolkit development). However, this task is dependable on other tasks from the WP3:

- Task 3.2 (Extensible VITALISE data model)
- Task 3.3 (Living Lab Infrastructure API and core communication modules)
- Task 3.6 (RAI Certified Node dataset curation, preservation, and provision of access for Living Lab access)
- Task 3.8 (VITALISE Portal for data discovery and federated data access)

From a technical perspective, the module for anonymisation and synthetic data generation has been designed and implemented using the Python programming language, Rabbitmq (open-source message broker) and well-established synthetic data generation libraries, like Synthetic Data Vault (SDV). Containerisation (Docker) and docker-compose technologies are used to deploy and integrate VITALISE ICT tools. Despite some experimental work that has been done to analyse different Synthetic Data Generation (SDG) models for time series or sequential data (DGAN, WGAN-GP...), open-source SDG libraries have been implemented into the shareable data publishing and access service.

Overall, this document presents (1) basic concepts on anonymisation and synthetic data generation, (2) the designed workflows for sharing anonymised and synthetic data with external researchers, and (3) specific experimental work done for analysing new SDG approaches for future incorporations. Although the designs, tools and experimental implementation described through the document may suffer modifications according to the needs defined in the GA, no significant changes regarding the general ideas and workflows are anticipated.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable is of report nature as specified in the GA. The aim is to present the techniques and workflows used in the VITALISE ICT tools to enable a shareable data publishing and access service based on the privacy, ethics and IPR legislation and policies established by each LL infrastructure. Specifically, the document refers to the anonymisation and synthetic data generation methods and workflows used and implemented for Task 3.4 (Anonymisation mechanism and Synthetic data engine toolkit development) of WP3. These methods are integrated into the VITALISE service architecture (presented previously in D3.1). Moreover, this report describes additional experimental implementations developed but not integrated into the VITALISE service. Finally, overall conclusions of the deliverable are provided.

1.2 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1 (this section)** provides information regarding the purpose of the document and its structure.
- **Section 2** gathers and explains basic concepts about anonymisation and synthetic data generation.
- **Section 3** describes the designed and implemented workflows for the shareable data publishing and access service, including anonymisation and synthetic data generation.
- **Section 4** presents experimental and scientific work implementation on synthetic data generation for the VITALISE project.
- **Section 5** provides concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2 Basis of anonymisation and synthetic data generation

This section gathers basic information about data anonymisation and synthetic data generation (SDG), together with a brief state of the art with the most recent and relevant technologies researched for the VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service.

The motivation for researching data anonymisation and SDG comes from the necessity of LLs for publishing and making real data accessible. For this to be possible, the data must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (*General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text*, n.d.). According to the GDPR, personal data can be defined as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. In general, it contemplates how this personal data must be managed and processed through a whole research process, mentioning that no trackable personal data can be published without the explicit consent of each participant. Consent must incorporate information regarding the research objective, possible risks, etc., potentially leading to restricted data access for External Researchers (ER). Therefore, to comply with legal requirements and overcome specific data access limitations, anonymisation and SDG techniques are proposed to make LL data shareable to ER.

2.1 Data anonymisation

According to ISO 29100:2011, anonymisation is the process of irreversibly altering personally identifiable information (PII) so that PII can no longer be identified directly or indirectly. According to El Emam, four techniques have been extensively used for data anonymisation: (1) randomisation, (2) permutation, (3) generalisation, and (4) pseudonymisation (Emam, 2013). Next, each of these techniques is explained.

- **Randomisation** involves modifying personal data attributes or variables by random values chosen following a pre-made random pattern. Examples of randomisation include replacing the names of subjects with other names of people of the same sex and ethnicity or replacing addresses of people with other addresses in the same city or region. Data perturbation or noise aggregation, which is based on incorporating systematic noise into the data, is another example of a randomisation technique that can maintain some correlations between variables. This type of anonymisation technique is preferred when the values of the anonymised dataset need to be realistic, and the data model cannot be changed. It can typically be found in software testing use cases.
- **Permutation** is simply based on interchanging values from subject to subject, a method that does not avoid privacy issues when new external data is obtained. This technique would also maintain some information from the real data. However, it would distort other parameters, which can result in interpretability and utility issues.
- **Generalisation** is based on replacing specific data points with generic values, using a less granular version of the same information. To compute and select those generic values, the most extended algorithm is *k-anonymity*. With this algorithm, the data attributes are clustered in groups of at least k subjects to compute the value range, the generic value that will be used to replace the data points. With this generalisation algorithm, it is almost impossible to drill down to any group of subjects with fewer than $k-1$ other subjects.
- **Pseudonymisation** aims to eliminate PII, for example, social security number, name, national identity number, etc., by using tokenised identifiers, random pseudonyms or hashed values. The limitation of this technique is that once both the pseudonymised dataset and the real dataset are accessed, the information gained by an attacker can be huge.

2.2 Synthetic Data Generation

Synthetic Data (SD) was proposed to preserve the subjects' privacy, follow the instructions on current regulations like the GDPR, and overcome the problems of traditional anonymisation methods. SD is typically defined in the literature as artificial data generated from original data and a model. Later this model is trained to reproduce the characteristics and structure of the original data,

as stated in the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) (*Synthetic Data | European Data Protection Supervisor, 2023*). SD is generated from statistical distributions that do not contain subject-specific information, and because it is inherently artificial, it can be used as a privacy-preserving, data augmentation or data balancing technology. Also, as SD is not considered real data and no specific mention is yet made in the GDPR, its usage could be free and open access for ERs in certain contexts.

Synthetic Data Generation (SDG) as an approach to data privacy started in 1993 with D. Rubin synthesising Decennial Census long-form responses for short-form households. In 1994, authors like Stephen E. Fienberg, John M. Abowd and Jim Woodcock contributed to the development of SD generation until a huge step was made in 2014 with the first Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) architecture (Nikolenko, 2021). Since then, different models and improvements have been published focusing on different topics, such as image, music, or time series generation. Table 1 compares traditional anonymisation techniques' performance and risks against SD generation.

Table 1: Comparison between traditional anonymisation techniques and SD.

Technique	Re-identification risk	Feature statistics	Feature correlations	ML performance
Synthetic Data Generation	None ¹	High	High	High
Randomisation	Medium	Medium	Low	Low
Permutation	High	High	Very Low	Low
Generalisation	Low	Low	Low	Low
Pseudonymisation	Very High	High	High	High

As for today, SD generation approaches are becoming increasingly accepted for biomedical applications as well, either for medical image generation (Pinaya et al., 2022) or Electronic Health Record (EHR) generation (Rankin et al., 2020). According to Hernandez et al., the most prevalent techniques used for SDG can be clustered into three main groups (Hernandez et al., 2022):

- **Classical approaches** can be defined as statistical and probabilistic models that attempt to simulate real data-capturing correlation structures. Supervised ML models have also been used for sequential SDG, taking the real data as input; this model type can predict the next sequences.
- **Deep Learning (DL) approaches** include neural networks and generative models that can produce highly realistic synthetic data. This category includes Autoencoders, GANs and ensembles.
- **Other** approaches are composed of several steps or modules. Most of these SDG approaches generate SD from statistics of publicly available data or using the knowledge extracted from original data.

¹ Subject to the correct usage of the techniques.

3 VITALISE Shareable data publishing and access service

This section will describe the VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service explaining the modules involved and the workflows followed for publishing and accessing shareable data. It must be mentioned that this service is part of the VITALISE service architecture designed to comply with the required ICT tools for the harmonisation, standardisation and public usage of data stored in different LLs. The complete VITALISE service architecture is explained and described in D3.1 (VITALISE Service Specification) of the project.

3.1 Description of the service

The VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service provides tools for external researchers (ER) to download shareable data (anonymised - model compliant and non-data model (NDM) compliant - and synthetic data) internally stored in LLs. ERs can use this downloaded data to develop, test and debug their processing scripts locally on highly realistic and representative shareable data without privacy risks. Then, they can request the remote execution of the same algorithms with the complete dataset (real data) stored internally in the LLs.

Since this deliverable is focused on shareable data algorithms, only the processes of downloading the different kinds of data are explained in this section. To better understand the complete workflow and architecture with other services and functionalities, you can review the D3.1 (VITALISE Service Specification).

3.2 Modules of the service

The VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service has been divided into two main modules (Discovery Portal and RAI Node) to facilitate the scalability, deployment and integration in the complete VITALISE service architecture. Each module is specialized in different tasks and communicates with the other ones. Next, each module is described, specifying its objectives regarding the referring service.

3.2.1 Discovery Portal (DP)

The DP, which is presented as a web-based GUI, is the common entry point for the different VITALISE ICT tools and ERs. ERs can use the DP to perform the following operations:

1. Explore, identify and query the LL available research data.
2. Interact with the RAI Node to download a shareable version of the desired data (anonymised - model compliant and NDM - and synthetic data).

The DP can be used for more actions, such as requesting the remote execution of experiments, but they are out of the scope of this deliverable. For more information about those functionalities, see D3.1 (VITALISE Service Specification).

3.2.2 RAI Node

The RAI Node is the software package installed in each LL. This software package is responsible for the following tasks:

1. Collect, prepare, and transform data gathered for each LL into the harmonised VITALISE data model.
2. Inform and update the DP on new datasets available.
3. Generate synthetic and shareable data representing real data produced in each LL, allowing ERs to develop algorithms locally.

The RAI Node can be used for more actions, such as the remote execution of experiments, but they are out of the scope of this deliverable. For more information about those functionalities, see D3.1 (VITALISE Service Specification).

3.3 Workflows for shareable data publishing and access

As shown in Figure 1, an ER can request either data model compliant data (anonymised or synthetic data generated from non-anonymised data) or non-data model (NDM) compliant data, already anonymised.

Figure 1: DP screenshot showing the different shareable data types that an ER can explore, query and request

Different workflows have been developed for publishing and accessing each data type to ensure that highly realistic and representative data is given to ERs with no privacy risks. In the following sections each workflow is described in more detail.

3.3.1 Data model compliant data

Inside the VITALISE service, the data model compliant data is defined as the LL data transformed to the standardised and harmonised VITALISE data model defined for the project, accessible in the following link: <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model>. Uploading data from different sources to the RAI Node entails a transformation to the defined VITALISE data format. More information about the VITALISE data model can be found in (Maga-Nteve et al., 2022).

The LL managers can register datasets and subjects to assign them an id, and then upload datapoints associated with these generated ids through the RAI Node. Each data model compliant datapoint must be linked to a dataset id and, optionally, to a subject. Data model compliant LL data points can be uploaded to the RAI Node after locally transforming them into the data model or from the source format. Only transformations for heart rate and steps from fitbit devices are available at the moment.

In the current working prototype of the VITALISE ICT tools, when a researcher wants to upload data, either in the source format or previously transformed, there are two ways to do it: Anonymising the data before uploading or non-anonymising before uploading, and then triggering within the RAI Node the generation of a synthetic version of the data. In the next sections, the workflows for publishing and accessing these kinds of data are explained.

3.3.1.1 Anonymised data

The workflow of the VITALISE service for anonymised data publishing and accessing is depicted in Figure 2. In this workflow, the LL manager must ensure that the data to be uploaded is previously anonymised with their preferred technique (pseudonymisation, generalisation, masking...) and follows the required input format for transforming it to the VITALISE data model.

To upload anonymised data to the RAI Node, LL managers should first create the dataset entry indicating that the dataset is anonymised. Then, they can upload the anonymised datapoints to the

created dataset. Once the anonymised datapoints are uploaded to the RAI Node, they are joined to the dataset for which the datapoints have been uploaded to then update metadata and statistics of the dataset in the DP.

ERs can then explore the available anonymised datasets metadata and statistics for all running RAI Nodes through the DP. ERs can inspect available datasets and query data from them, filtering it by subject's gender or age, dataset id and/or data types (heart rate, steps...). When a request is done to the DP, the anonymised data is queried in the RAI Node, and a limited version of 1000 rows of the query results is returned to the ER through the DP.

Figure 2: VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service for anonymised data

3.3.1.2 Synthetic data

The workflow of the VITALISE service for non-anonymised or sensitive data publishing and SD versions accessing is depicted in Figure 3 and is presented in (Hernandez et al., 2022). In this workflow, the LL manager must ensure that the data follows the required input format for transforming it into the VITALISE data model.

To upload non anonymised data or sensitive data to the RAI Node, LL controllers should first create the dataset entry indicating that the dataset is not anonymised. Then, they can upload non anonymised datapoints to the created dataset. Once the sensitive datapoints are uploaded to the RAI Node, they are joined to the associated dataset and metadata and statistics are updated in the DP.

In the RAI Node, an SDG model is trained and used to generate SD from the uploaded non anonymised datasets. This generated synthetic data is locally stored in the SD database. In the current prototype version of the service, an open-source SDG model from the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) library is used (Patki et al., 2016; *The Synthetic Data Vault. Put Synthetic Data to Work!*, n.d.). More advanced SDG models, experimentally tested and presented in Section 4 of this document, will be incorporated in the future, together with a methodology to select the most appropriate SDG model, depending on the input data.

ERs can then explore the available non anonymised datasets metadata and statistics for all running RAI Nodes through the DP. This functionality allows to inspect these datasets and query data for all of them, filtering it by subject's gender or age, dataset id and data types (heart rate, steps...). When

this request is done to the DP, the SD database is queried in the RAI Node, and a limited version of 1000 rows of the query result is returned to the ER through the DP. The limitation of 1000 rows is to avoid memory issues.

Figure 3: VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service for synthetic data

3.3.2 Non data model (NDM) compliant data

The NDM compliant data is data from LLs that cannot be transformed to the VITALISE data model for whatever reason (format incompatibilities, data gathering process...). In the current prototype version, this data type must be anonymised before a LL controller uploads it to the RAI Node, and only CSV files are allowed to be uploaded.

The workflow of the VITALISE service for NDM data publishing and accessing is depicted in Figure 4. In this workflow, the LL manager must ensure that: 1) the data to be uploaded is previously anonymised and 2) that the data file to be uploaded is a valid CSV file with the following characteristics:

- Use of commas as the separator.
- Only one header row with non-duplicated column names is used.
- At least one row of data can be found.

To upload NDM data to the RAI Node, LL controllers should fill the dataset fields (name, author, description...) and select the valid CSV file previously anonymised. Once the NDM data is uploaded in the RAI Node, metadata and statistics of the NDM dataset are sent to the DP.

ERs can then explore the available NDM datasets metadata and statistics for all running RAI Nodes through the DP. This functionality allows to inspect these datasets and choose the desired NDM dataset across all the available ones in all RAI Nodes registered in the DP. When this request is done to the DP, the NDM dataset is found in the RAI Node, and a limited version of 1000 rows of the NDM dataset is returned to the ER through the DP.

Figure 4: VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service for NDM compliant data

3.4 Limitations and Future Work

With the current version of the VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service incorporated in the VITALISE ICT tools service architecture, ERs can query and download VITALISE data model compliant data (anonymised or synthesized) and NDM data. Nonetheless, the actual prototype working in some LLs has limitations to overcome for future prototypes.

First, the VITALISE data model compliant workflows (anonymised and synthetic data) are only compatible with heart rate and step measurements from Fitbit devices. Also, if a LL controller wants to upload data already transformed to the VITALISE data model, only heart rate, steps, and body temperature measurements can be uploaded. For future versions of the VITALISE ICT tools service, more data types will be incorporated as soon as LL data is available.

For the VITALISE data model compliant anonymised data workflow, there is no way other than the LL controller confirmation to assure that the uploaded data is truly anonymised. Thus, future versions of the anonymised data will incorporate the option of performing anonymisation (with the techniques explained in Section 2.1) to the data when uploading if requested by the LL controller.

A simple and open-source SDG approach is used to generate synthetic data for the VITALISE data model compliant synthetic data workflow. This is enough for initial debugging and prototyping, but more complex and customized SDG models, such as GAN-based approaches, will be integrated in the future. Additionally, a report with SD metrics will be returned to the ER for every synthetic data request they do.

Only CSV files with specific characteristics can be uploaded and accessed through the explained service regarding the NDM data workflow. For future versions of the service, other data files and types will be available to upload, such as JSON format.

3.5 Related publications

The following publications related to the explained VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service have been published.

- Maga-Nteve, C., Epelde, G., Hernandez, M., Tsolakis, N., Konstantinidis, E., Meditskos, G., Bamidis, P., & Vrochidis, S. (2022). Standardized and extensible reference data model for clinical research in Living Labs. *Procedia Computer Science*, 210, 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.10.133>
 - This conference publication presents the VITALISE data model developed and followed to standardise and harmonise LLs data.
- Hernandez, M., Epelde, G., Beristain, A., Álvarez, R., Molina, C., Larrea, X., Alberdi, A., Timoleon, M., Bamidis, P., & Konstantinidis, E. (2022). Incorporation of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques within a Controlled Data Processing Workflow in the Health and Wellbeing Domain. *Electronics*, 11(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11050812>
 - This journal publication presents the first synthetic data access service version highlighting how SDG models can be incorporated into a controlled data processing workflow.

4 Experimental work on synthetic data generation

This section is fully dedicated to exploring the potential of SDG. In this sense, the demand for high-quality data is continuously growing, but some domains are more extensively researched than others. The generation of Time Series (TS) is falling behind its transversal counterpart, as inherent limitations of longitudinal data synthesis (e.g., the need to learn temporal correlations between samples) hinder the application of innovative techniques for the task.

Section 4.1 explains why this component of the VITALISE project was experimentally performed, along with the potential difficulties that were considered at the beginning of the development phase. Section 4.2 describes the technical developments that were carried out for the Synthetic Time Series Generation (STSG), and the results are presented in section 4.3. Lastly, the limitations of our work and the identified future lines are presented in 4.4. The publications derived from the work in this section can be found in section 4.5.

4.1 Motivation

The data provided by LLs come from diverse sources. A considerable percentage of that data is longitudinal, comprising information about subjects' health- or performance-related information (e.g., fitbit data with the number of steps). Considering the nature of the data and the difficulties encountered in creating time series, an experimental approach was considered to fulfil this task.

4.2 Synthetic Time Series Generation (STSG) with Subject's Metadata

The capacity of a TS to embed compromised information remains an unresolved issue in the current scientific literature. Currently, there is no consensus on whether data from one or multiple TS offers enough information to identify a specific person, instance, or sample among several ones. That is why the VITALISE project has put effort into researching the topic thoroughly by considering three different environments for generating synthetic data that warrants a proper level of privacy and maintains the utility of the data.

In subsections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2, the work published by Larrea et al. (Larrea et al., 2022) is presented, where two approaches are presented to find the most optimal method for synthesising subjects. Section 4.3.3 presents the work published by Isasa et al., where a third possibility is also considered (Isasa et al., 2023).

4.2.1 A1: Synthetic metadata coupled with real Time Series

The first approach can be thought of as generating partially synthetic subjects since only metadata is synthetically generated and then real TS is joined to the generated synthetic metadata. Schiff et al. (Schiff et al., 2018) inspired this approach as they proposed to enrich synthetic subjects' metadata with real TS. This approach overcomes the original idea of adding a coupling step to the workflow.

As can be seen in Figure 5, only the metadata component of the dataset is synthesized (to which statistics of the TS are added) and then coupled with real TS using statistical methods. The idea behind the coupling step is to link the metadata component with the best-fitting longitudinal component to create synthetic subjects that are as accurate and realistic as possible.

Figure 5. Generation of synthetic patients with synthetic metadata and real time series. Inspired by Larrea et al. (Larrea et al., 2022)

The statistical coupling proposed in the research was based on calculating the mean value of all Euclidean distances between each synthetic and real TS statistic. All the statistics are previously normalized, and the TS data that outputs the lowest distance sum is attached to the synthesized subject metadata. The pseudo-code for the coupling method can also be found in the original publication (Larrea et al., 2022).

4.2.2 A2: Synthetic metadata coupled with synthetic Time Series

The outcome of the second approach is fully synthetic, as both the metadata and the TS are generated. This second approach can be considered a first step forward from the A1, as STSG methods are used.

Figure 6 shows the workflow for the second approach. Note that even if TS is managed to be synthesized, the process is still divided into two subprocesses: The metadata generation with TS statistics (1) and the TS generation (2). The results of both subprocesses are then coupled using the same approach presented in section 4.2.1.

Figure 6. Generation of synthetic patients with synthetic metadata and synthetic time series. Inspired by Larrea et al. (Larrea et al., 2022)

4.2.3 Joint generation of synthetic metadata and Time Series

The most recently published STSG models have hypothesized the incorporation of metadata to the TS generation, a factor that may improve the overall quality of the synthetic outcome. It is the case for the DGAN, which also divides the generation process into two subtasks but uses the synthetic metadata to conditionally generate TS. Another example is the WGAN-GP (Lin et al., 2020), in which the model's loss function is modified according to the correlation coefficient between variables (metadata and TS).

In work presented by Isasa et al., these two models that incorporate differently the metadata to the TS generation are compared (Isasa et al., 2023). In both cases, statistical coupling methods are unnecessary, as the outcome of the trained models already follows the original data scheme.

4.3 Results

The first two approaches were validated using standardized metrics and methods proposed by Hernandez et al. (Hernandez et al., 2023). The used dataset consisted of Treadmill Maximal Exercise

Tests (Mongin et al., n.d.) selected from Physionet (Goldberger et al., 2000), which incorporated both metadata and TS for 992 experiments. The research on STSG was finally carried out with 950 experiments containing 228 measurements each after pre-processing the dataset by deleting instances with missing values in the metadata and/or more than 5% missing values in the temporal sequence. The analysis showed that the approach involving real TS coupling is functional, while the alternative approach needs further research.

The results of the third approach were tested using two different datasets, the first being the same TMET data presented previously. As a second dataset, a subset was derived from the MIMIC-III v1.4 database, containing hypotensive (MAP > 65 mmHg) adult (>18 years) patients' longitudinal data. For this second dataset, 674 patients were evaluated for sequences of 48 hourly measurements each. Intervariable correlation maps were calculated to analyse the effect of the joint generation, and different results were obtained for different models, emphasizing the importance of jointly generating metadata and TS. Even if both analysed models appeared to be competitive in terms of resemblance and utility, they also raised privacy concerns.

Figure 7. Correlation maps for the TMET data (upper) and hypotension data (lower).

4.4 Limitations and Future Work

The validation of the first two approaches has limitations that must be addressed in future work. First, the privacy-related affairs of the generated data were not extensively analysed, which is the main concern of the SDG. Also, the approaches were evaluated using a single dataset, which may lead to dataset-specific results. Lastly, the quality of the proposed coupling method was not evaluated, as different ones may appear depending on the use case.

The main limitation of the third approach was the lack of a golden rule to evaluate the quality of synthetic time series. Therefore, the evaluation was carried out by using and adapting existing standardised metrics for tabular transversal data. The creation or standardisation of TS-specific metrics is considered for future research. Also, the privacy of the data was the dimension that fell the furthest from our expectations, and therefore improving those will be prioritized. Incorporating these improved models to the VITALISE ICT tool was considered in the near to middle future.

4.5 Related publications

The experimental work on SDG explained in this section has led to the following related publications:

- Larrea, X., Hernandez, M., Epelde, G., Beristain, A., Molina, C., Alberdi, A., Rankin, D., Bamidis, P., & Konstantinidis, E. (2022). Synthetic Subject Generation with Coupled Coherent Time Series Data. *Engineering Proceedings*, 18(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.3390/engproc2022018007>
 - This work was presented in the ITISE 2022 conference first and published in *Engineering Proceedings* afterwards. Shortly, the real necessity of generating synthetic TS is evaluated by presenting three different STSG approaches.
- Isasa, I., Hernandez, M., Epelde, G., Londoño, F., Beristain, A., Alberdi, A., Bamidis, P., & Konstantinidis, E. (2023). Effect of incorporating metadata to the generation of synthetic time series in a healthcare context. *2023 IEEE 36th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)*, 910–916. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS58004.2023.00341>
 - This work was presented at the CBMS 2023 conference. Following the approaches in the previous publication, the effect of incorporating metadata into the TS generation is analysed using two different SDG models.

5 Conclusion

This document, which corresponds to D3.3 Anonymisation and Synthetic Data Algorithm and is of report nature, describes the VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service related to the VITALISE ICT tools being developed in WP3. This deliverable presents some basics of anonymisation and synthetic data generation, the designed workflows for making LL data shareable and accessible to ERs, and some experimental work related to SDG for a future incorporation of SDG models in the described workflows.

The VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service explained in the document provides tools for ERs to download GDPR-compliant shareable data (anonymised, synthetic, and NDM data) internally stored in LLs without privacy risks. ERs can use this downloaded data to develop, test and debug their processing scripts locally on highly realistic and representative shareable data and then request the remote execution of the same algorithms with the (real) data stored internally in the LLs. Additionally, some background about anonymisation and SDG is provided, and some experimental work developed on SDG for the LLs data is presented.

The document starts by explaining what anonymisation and SDG are and why they are needed for sharing internally stored data in LLs (Section 2). Next, the VITALISE shareable data publishing and access service is presented, describing the different workflows an ER can follow to download different types of shareable data (data model compliant anonymised or synthetic data, and NDM data) (Section 3). Finally, some experimental work developed on SDG for time series data is presented (Section 4).

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